

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES

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ANNUAL REPORT TO FOUNDATIONS

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COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES, INC.

Annual Report, 1981-1982

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1. Deceased, April, 1982.

2. Deceased, December, 1981.

3. Mr. Cole was elected to succeed Mr. Wells at the November 1981 annual meeting.

4. Deceased, September, 1981.

PROGRAM HIGHLIGHTS

Note: The published version of this report will contain an Introduction by Warren J. Haas, President, Council on Library Resources, Inc.

BIBLIOGRAPHIC SERVICES

The Council's Bibliographic Service Development Program (BSDP) began its fourth year in November, 1981. Focused on assuring access to a comprehensive set of bibliographic record databases, the development of required products from those databases, and helping control costs of bibliographic processes in libraries, BSDP activities continued on several fronts. During the year, substantial progress was made in a number of program areas, especially the evaluation of online public access catalogs, and linking bibliographic computer systems. Preparatory work for another program area, subject access, also has been started.

The activities related to linking computer systems deserve special comment. As the possibilities for building a national bibliographic record database were explored during the early stages of the BSDP, it became evident that such a database was not economically feasible, but that the same effect could be gained by constructing links between the existing major bibliographic databases. To build links that would extend the use of one system to users of

other computer systems requires that a host of technical problems be solved. Linking computer systems is the focus of several BSDP projects, and it is a task that requires attention to both the content of what will be transmitted and the protocols and telecommunication hardware needed to accomplish the task. The impact of these projects on libraries will be substantial, because the work will make possible the communication of many kinds of data in addition to bibliographic records. Moreover, computing applications of all kinds may be affected by the development of the telecommunication protocols described below.

During fiscal 1982, over 40 BSDP grants were active, and funding amounting to over \$2 million was administered through the program. As a guide to the wide-ranging efforts to improve bibliographic services, the projects are described below under broad, topical headings.

Standards and Guides

Recognizing the need for consistent and dependable methods of accomplishing agreed-on tasks, the BSDP has devoted a great deal of effort to helping develop codes, protocols, and standards. Standard methods are required to assist nearly every aspect of bibliographic record sharing. The contents of catalog records, records for nonbook materials, communication formats, and the means of receiving and communicating information all have been subjects for BSDP attention during the past four years. This year, several BSDP participants have been involved in a long effort to develop sets

of rules, or protocols, that govern how information is transmitted from one computer to another.

System Network Interconnection (SNI)

The Research Libraries Group (RLG), the Washington Library Network (WLN), and the Library of Congress (LC), are developing a standard means of linking computer systems. OCLC, Inc., also is involved in this work in an advisory and support capacity. The project will produce a set of telecommunication protocols that can be used by computer systems to communicate with other computer systems. The work builds on existing telecommunication standards--the Open Systems Model of the International Standards Organization. The model is designed in seven layers, and because the lower levels already have been developed, the RLG/WLN/LC portion of the work is directed toward levels 4, 5, and 6. A description of the proposed network, titled Network Topology Document, has been completed. The project has been funded for fourteen months, beginning in February, 1982.

The seventh and final layer of the protocol, called the Application Level Protocol, is being developed at Northwestern University. As the year ended, participants learned of similar work in progress in Canada. A supplementary grant assists coordination of their work with the Canadian protocol development.

American National Standards Committee Z-39

The current BSDP support for Committee Z-39 is intended to assist progress on standards related to holdings information in bibliographic records, and telecommunication protocols. CLR funding also is provided for

work related to book paper quality.

Character Sets

A BSDP grant provided travel funds for a staff member from the Library of Congress Network Development Office to attend a Paris meeting of the International Standards Organization's Working Group on Character Sets.

Non-Roman Character Sets

OCLC, Inc. received a grant in 1978 to develop a non-Roman character set capability for computerized input, storage, processing and display of bibliographic information. For organizational and economic reasons, OCLC has withdrawn from this project.

Serials Cancellation

A 1981 grant went to the Pittsburgh Regional Library Center to develop a prototype system for recording and communicating subscription cancellation decisions via an on-line union list. The project is scheduled to be completed in late 1982.

Linking Bibliographic Databases

Linked Systems Project (LSP)

The Linked Systems Project, formerly called the Linked Authority Systems Project, is central to the goals of the BSDP. The project goal is to develop,

coordinate, and link the bibliographic and computer systems of three organizations: the Washington Library Network (WLN), the Research Libraries Group, Inc. (RLG), and the Library of Congress (LC), so that they can exchange bibliographic records and other information. In effect, these links will provide the technical environment required for a national bibliographic record service.

This large project involves several different kinds of tasks. One group is developing computer-to-computer protocols. These efforts are part of the technical elaboration needed to link computer systems, and because the technical requirements involve standards development, some of this basic work has been described above, under "Standards and Guides." The second group is designing software to translate the language of individual computer systems into the language of the telecommunication link. It also is planning to test the link through the exchange of authority records. The authorities implementation will utilize the work of the Task Force on a Name Authority File Service (NAFS).

During the first two phases of the LSP, participants conducted an assessment of the feasibility of linking systems, and defined a plan for accomplishing the work. RLG and WLN received assistance for their work in making necessary changes in their authorities systems to allow computer exchange of that information. Also, planning for the hardware and software required to achieve the link was carried on, and the telecommunication system itself was the subject of extensive analysis.

Two reports describe some of the work carried on during these first phases. The Authorities Group submitted LASP Functional Specifications: Intersystem Component (March, 1981), which contains the specifications for the search and response, file maintenance and message functions of the linked

systems. The Telecommunications Group completed Protocol Evaluation, Survey of Network Offerings, Traffic Estimates and Assessment of Investment in Linkage (March, 1981).

While the work of the Authorities and Telecommunications Groups progressed, a separate Task Force on a Name Authority File Service was studying the requirements for operating the planned NAFS. In April, 1981, the Task Force completed its Requirements Statement for a Name Authority File Service, and circulated it for comment from the library community. During late 1981 and early 1982 the group revised the document, and completed guidelines for Service operation and for the selection of contributing institutions. NAFS will be operated by the Library of Congress.

The Authorities Group has taken the requirements listed by the Task Force and incorporated them into its LSP External Design: Intersystem Component (February, 1982). This document contains detailed specifications for software required to translate commands from each system into the language of the telecommunications link and back again into system language.

Bibliographic Products

During the late seventies and early eighties, two separate developments came together to provide a new means of accessing bibliographic information. One of these developments is specific to libraries: the construction of large machine-readable databases of catalog records. The second development is more general: the application of technology to make possible widespread access to

computerized databases. Libraries began to build their databases during the seventies. These databases are now being made available to library users in the form of online public access catalogs (OPACs), and many important questions regarding online use of bibliographic products require attention. The BSDP has begun this process through a set of online catalog evaluation studies.

Online Public Access Catalog (OPAC) Evaluation

Early in 1981, six groups began a two-year project to evaluate online public access catalogs (OPACs) nationwide. Current participants in the project are J. Matthews & Associates, OCLC, Inc., the Research Libraries Group (RLG), the University of California, Division of Library Automation, and the Library of Congress. Due to circumstances beyond its control, the University of Toronto Library Automated System (UTLAS), which had planned to participate, had to withdraw from the project.

During the first phase of the project, participants designed and tested questionnaires and other evaluation tools required for data collection. Northwestern University Library, Stanford University Library, and Dartmouth College Library received assistance to cover their participation in these preliminary planning activities. OCLC, Inc., als, received funding to support training activities for data collection interviewers.

The main data collection was performed during April and May, 1982. The University of California, Division of Library Automation, with the aid of another BSDP grant, has undertaken the machine analysis of data collected by all participants in the project. A major report based on project research already has been published: Charles Hildreth's Online Public Access Catalogs: The User Interface (Dublin, Ohio, 1982). Early results of the data collection

also have influenced another BSDP initiative: the investigation of subject access questions.

Subject Authority Structure

BSDP examination of problems relating to subject access to materials in research libraries began last year when Carol Mandel and Judith Herschman produced a paper titled "Subject Access in the Online Catalog." The paper provided an overview of research in the area, and pointed out some prospects for improving subject access. Findings from the OPAC study substantiate the need to pursue research on subject access. Whereas in most card catalog use studies only about one-fifth of the initial searches were by subject, the OPAC users begin nearly two-thirds of their efforts with a subject search. This result reinforced the decision to devote attention to subject access needs.

In June, 1982, the BSDP organized a meeting of 23 specialists in the area of subject access to discuss current knowledge about the topic, and recommend ways to improve existing systems. Participants specified a number of changes and improvements that would require both short- and long-term projects. The draft recommendations currently are being reviewed by the group.

Subject Headings

The Council has contracted with Pauline Atherton Cochrane to develop a plan to enhance the cross reference structure of the Library of Congress Subject Headings (LCSH). A progress report titled "Current Cross Reference Practice in LCSH--Its Impact on Online Searching" has been received. The project is scheduled to be completed in October, 1982.

Conversion of Serials (CONSER)

The Conversion of Serials (CONSER) project is a cooperative effort among libraries to build a database of bibliographic records for serial publications. In the past, the Council has provided funding to support CONSER management and for projects related to building the database. Currently, several CONSER-related projects are receiving support.

Theological Journals

The Boston Theological Institute is adding to the CONSER database titles in the area of religion and theology. A grant has been made to support telecommunication costs during input of additional entries required, due to changes in the cataloging rules.

Abstracting and Indexing Coverage

The BSDP provided funds to support travel costs for participants in an August, 1981, Association of Research Libraries-National Federation of Abstracting and Indexing Services meeting to develop a plan for adding information to the CONSER database. The group developed a proposal to input information on which indexing and abstracting services include titles in the CONSER database. The information would be added to the records for each title covered.

Telecommunication Costs

The Council continues to support telecommunication costs for CONSER participation by the National Library of Canada.

Bibliographic Products

Bibliographic Records on Microcomputers

Victor Rosenberg, University of Michigan School of Library Science, has received a BSDP grant to produce computer programs to extract and reformat bibliographic records from shared cataloging service databases, such as OCLC and the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN).

MARC Record Analysis

In June, 1982, the Council received the final report on a project to compile statistics on the MARC database. Martha Williams, University of Illinois Coordinated Science Laboratory, investigated changes in record length, field tag occurrences, and field lengths for records produced during the period 1973-1981. She also has analyzed relationships over time among selected fields within records.

AACR-II Catalog Headings

An assessment of the differences in Anglo-American Cataloging Rules (AACR-II) applications in four national libraries is being conducted by Donald Cook, University of Toronto. Cook's study focuses on unplanned variations in headings for names of persons and corporate bodies established by the National Library of Australia, the National Library of Canada, the British Library, and the Library of Congress.

Access to Bibliographic Data

New ways of accessing bibliographic data and publications are appearing because the advent of machine readable databases has made such alternatives possible. To address the access questions, several BSDP projects concentrate on evaluating the use of databases and the addition of new capabilities for accessing and delivering information.

Network Advisory Committee

The BSDP has provided support for two meetings of the Network Advisory Committee to the Library of Congress during the year. The meetings focused on the need to improve the delivery of information as a direct response to improved identification of locations through online bibliographic databases.

Cataloging in Publication Program

In 1980, the Council provided funds to the Cataloging in Publication Division of the Library of Congress for an evaluation of the program's effectiveness and impact. The report on the evaluation, titled CIP Survey Final Report, was received in May, 1982.

ARL Microform Project

The Association of Research Libraries received a BSDP grant in March, 1981, for activities intended to help improve bibliographic access to the contents of microform collections. During the first year of the two-year project, a survey was conducted to obtain information on libraries' current cataloging efforts, existing catalog records, and other related activities.

Machine-Readable Humanities Texts

BSDP funds support Rutgers University's project to build an international inventory of machine-readable texts in the humanities. Data on existing texts will be received through responses to a questionnaire, and the information will be prepared for subsequent input as a specific database in the Research Libraries Information Network (RLIN). A microfiche catalog also will be produced.

PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION, TRAINING, AND RESEARCH

The Council's Professional Education and Training for Research Librarianship (PETREL) program entered its second year in fiscal 1982. The program has provided funding for three major professional education programs, and other activities aimed at improving education, training, and other opportunities for professional growth. In June, 1982, the PETREL Advisory Committee invited a group of library school deans, library directors and personnel officers to a two-day meeting to discuss the place of internships in professional education, and to consider other topics pertaining to careers in librarianship. The Committee's aim was to gather opinions on both current program efforts and possible new endeavors. The Council will issue a report and evaluation of the first year of the PETREL program, which will include the substance of the June discussions.

In addition to the PETREL grants, the Council has provided assistance for several other projects related to research and training. The Management Intern Program, which began in the mid-seventies, did not operate during the past year, but it will resume in the fall of 1982 with the selection of a

ninth group of interns.

Education for Health Sciences Librarianship

The report of a PETREL-funded investigation into the Medical Library Association's role in educating health sciences librarians was issued in October, 1981. Titled MLA's Role in the Educational Process for Health Sciences Librarians, the report describes past MLA commitments and recommends future Association action in this area.

Basic Professional Education

The University of Michigan School of Library Science has developed a special curriculum for students who plan to enter university and research librarianship. Graduates will receive the Master of Arts in Library Science. PETREL funding provided for this program is primarily for student aid.

Advanced Study in Library Management

A program to advance working professionals' knowledge of management theory and practice, and to prepare them for middle and upper management positions in research libraries, has begun at the University of Chicago Graduate Library School. Graduates will receive a Certificate of Advanced Study in Library Management. PETREL support of this program provides student stipends.

Senior Fellows

The Graduate School of Library and Information Science at the University of California, Los Angeles, is operating a Senior Fellows Program scheduled to begin in August, 1982, and to run for two additional years. Interdisciplinary

coursework, a seminar on current library management issues, and individual research projects are planned for the Fellows, all of whom hold upper level posts in academic library administration. PETREL support is provided for the first three classes of Fellows.

Frontiers Conference

"The University Environment Through 2000" was the theme of the first frontiers conference funded by the PETREL program and hosted by the Graduate School of Library and Information Science, University of California, Los Angeles, in December, 1981. Forty-nine invited participants from libraries, library schools, university administration, and associations gathered to discuss the effects of changes in academic institutions on their research libraries.

Research Support

As the year ended, a new PETREL project was launched: research support for joint projects by faculty members and library directors. Those teams whose projects receive funding will be given small grants to cover the incremental costs of their research.

Faculty Development in Information Science

A project underway during fiscal 1981 at C.W. Post Center, Long Island University, was extended to include the fall semester of 1981. The project goal was to prepare faculty members from C.W. Post, St. John's University, and Queens College to teach introductory information science courses to be integrated into the library school curriculum.

British Academic Library Research

Jovana J. Brown, Evergreen State College, has received a CLR grant to study the British Library Research and Development Department funding of academic library research in Great Britain. Her project focuses on trends and patterns in funding, and includes case studies of projects at several university research units.

Academic Library Management Intern Program

The Council's Management Intern Program was suspended during fiscal 1982, pending its evaluation by CLR staff, program participants, and others. For the program review, the Council invited past interns and directors who served as hosts to comment on aspects of their experience, especially on their opinions about its lasting value. Their replies made it clear that both hosts and interns believe that the program provides a unique and important experience that enhances participants' career opportunities.

During the spring of 1982, the Council made preparations to select a 1983-1984 class of interns, and to resume the program.

LIBRARY RESOURCES AND THEIR PRESERVATION

Helping provide the collections and information resources needed to support effective library use is the continuing focus of this part of the Council's programs. Preservation needs no longer require documentation, but finding effective and fiscally responsible methods for restoring, maintaining and protecting collections is an ongoing concern. A special CLR committee has devoted two years to efforts to make librarians, publishers, and others evaluate more carefully the materials used in book manufacturing. The goal is to prevent at least some future preservation problems.

The development of library resources is closely related to collection development programs and research in library use. Users' needs according to their fields of interest, current collecting patterns, and improved indexing and location services are all topics of concern in this area. Council interests in library resources therefore range from expanding current knowledge about user needs to assistance for the production of reference books and aids to research.

Longevity in Paper and Binding

The Council's Committee on Production Guidelines for Book Longevity continued its work during 1981-1982. During the past year, the group has concentrated on evaluating materials used in book bindings and assessing the current use of acid-free paper in the U.S. publishing community. A report on the characteristics of paper used by publishers was completed for the committee. Near the end of the year, an interim report titled Longevity in Book Binding was issued. With most of its planned work completed, the Committee will issue a final report incorporating the reports on book paper and bindings, and a summary of the survey of publishers. The Council will publish the report in pamphlet form.

Choice Periodical List

The Council's support for a regular column in Choice magazine was initiated in 1975. The column provides evaluations of new periodicals and serials for college and university libraries.

British Library Resources

Robert B. Downs, of the University of Illinois, has published British and Irish Library Resources: A Bibliographical Guide. This 1981 publication is the second edition of the Guide, which was first published in 1972. A CLR grant assisted Downs' travel to the British Isles to do the research for the book.

Leaders in Librarianship

Wayne Wiegand, University of Kentucky, is the coordinator of a three-year project to produce essays on 15 prominent academic library leaders who were

active during the period 1925-1975. In late 1981, the Journal of Academic Librarianship published several of the essays. A book-length collection of all the essays is being prepared.

Byzantine Bindings

Using materials in the collection of the Monastery of St. John, Patmos, Greece, John Lawrence Sharpe III of Duke University and Guy Petherbridge, a consultant, are gathering information on Byzantine bindings dating from the twelfth through the sixteenth centuries. Because little is known about Greek codicology, their research concentrates on collecting information on a small body of manuscripts and constructing a profile of traditional Greek bookbinding features.

Collection Assessment

Four member libraries of the Cooperative College Library Center, a cooperative processing unit based in Atlanta, are testing the Association of Research Libraries' Office of Management Studies collection assessment manual. The manual was produced as part of an earlier CLR project. Atlanta College of Art, Dillard University, Tougaloo College and Tuskegee Institute finished their studies in June, 1982.

LIBRARY OPERATIONS AND SERVICES

The Council maintains a strong interest in research library operations, including management, services, and economic matters. A number of grants have helped individual libraries establish bibliographic instruction programs, improve communications with faculty, and experiment with ways to enhance the library's role in the teaching and learning process. Similarly, CLR has encouraged the study of management issues and recently provided funds for a meeting to discuss current issues in research library economics.

Access to library resources is a topic that is receiving more and more attention from both librarians and library users. Bibliographic systems have improved rapidly during recent years--more rapidly than libraries' ability to deliver information and materials to users. Locating the materials that are needed and finding the fastest and most inexpensive ways to obtain them are problems that librarians have tried to solve through special agreements, local cooperation, and enhanced delivery and communication capabilities. However, the existing delivery systems need to be improved, and some of the underlying

questions about access to materials have not been answered. In order to improve library services, it is important to know how location of material relates to its use, what kind of subject access to bibliographic records is most satisfactory, and what options for storing and delivering materials are most cost effective. These and other economic, legal, and operational questions require further exploration.

Academic Library Program

This program began in 1978 when the Council, the Carnegie Corporation of New York, and others, provided support for the Association of Research Libraries Office of Management Studies' efforts to improve library management. The OMS operates self-study programs for academic and research libraries, and in 1979 the Office implemented a new Consultant Training Program, with Council assistance. During 1980 and 1981, forty selected librarians received specialized training to become library management consultants. A third class of trainees was selected in June 1982.

Faculty - Library Communication

Participants in a CLR-supported Association of Research Libraries-American Association for the Advancement of the Humanities meeting in 1981 recommended that faculty members receive more information regarding problems and issues faced by libraries at their institutions. Accordingly, the Council funded the experimental distribution of a monthly newsletter, Library Issues, to faculty at three institutions: the University of Colorado, the University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill, and Princeton University. The objective is to improve faculty awareness and understanding of library issues.

College Library Program

Now in its last two years of operation, this program has involved 35 college and university libraries in projects designed to enhance the library's role on campus. Participants have constructed their own programs, but most have used the funding to institute or improve bibliographic instruction and other course-related activities. Nine libraries are still pursuing programs scheduled to last three-to-five years under the terms of the grants. During fiscal 1982, Ball State University, the University of Evansville, St. Olaf College, and Johnson C. Smith University completed their final reports. The remaining participants are scheduled to complete the program in 1983.

Bibliographic Instruction Workshops

CLR grants to Earlham College in 1981 provided funding for the sixth and seventh Conferences on Bibliographic Instruction, held in April, 1982, and planned for spring, 1983, respectively. The funding assists faculty travel to the Conferences.

Access to Materials in Storage

Late in 1981, the University of Michigan Library received a CLR grant to conduct a study of faculty attitudes toward locating and obtaining materials in storage. Project researchers proposed improvements in the current system that include more frequent deliveries of stored materials and better bibliographic access via online data bases, with terminals located in three humanities departments: History, English, and American Studies. Project activities have been delayed due to staffing changes at the Library, but work

is expected to begin early in 1983.

Archives Self-Study and Review

The Society of American Archivists (SAA) is conducting a project to establish a self-study and evaluation process for archival agencies. Six institutions tested the study process and the accompanying documentation in 1981, and project coordinators have revised the materials in preparation for final SAA approval and publication.

Association of American Universities (AAU)

A cooperative CLR-AAU project began in 1981 when the two organizations sponsored a meeting of twelve university officials, librarians, and foundation executives to discuss major issues facing research libraries. Task forces were formed to address five specific topics: bibliographic data bases and access to bibliographic information; resource sharing; preservation; technological applications; and research librarianship. By mid-1982, the task forces had finished their work, and plans were under way for advancing action on their findings and recommendations.

The Records of Government

Prompted by archivists' and scholars' concerns over the procedures and methods used to acquire, preserve, and distribute government records, the Council invited representatives of a number of institutions and associations to a June, 1982 meeting to consider suitable ways to address those concerns. The group has endorsed a major effort to find solutions to problems that concern archives and their users, and funding is being sought to support the work of a planned committee on government records.

INTERNATIONAL PROGRAMS

The Council's support for international activities is directed, for the most part, to projects similar to those described in other sections of this report. Helping remove barriers to the exchange of bibliographic information, encouraging development of standards to facilitate that exchange, and assisting other countries to adopt existing codes and guidelines are examples of such projects. Most of the CLR funding continues to be channeled through international organizations.

The Exxon Education Foundation provided two general support grants for CLR international programs in 1979 and 1980. A third grant from the Foundation was received in 1981.

Copyright and International Exchange of Bibliographic Data

The International Federation of Library Associations and Institutions (IFLA) received a CLR grant in 1979 to study copyright law and the implications for international exchange of machine-readable bibliographic data. In early 1982, King Research Inc. completed The IFLA International

Study of Copyright of Bibliographic Records in Machine Readable Form. The report recommends bilateral exchange agreements among national bibliographic agencies as the most feasible current mechanism for governing the exchange of machine-readable bibliographic data.

Library Materials for the Handicapped

The 1979 grant to IFLA also supported preparation of a study of specialized aspects of copyright law: Copyright and Library Materials for the Handicapped, by Francoise Hebert and Wanda Noel. Completed in 1981, the book will be made ready for publication with the help of a 1982 CLR follow-up grant. IFLA also will use part of the funds to pursue the recommendations included in the study.

International Cataloging in Publication (CIP)

The IFLA International Office for Universal Bibliographic Control has organized an international meeting to consider the standards for and implementation of cataloging in publication programs. Publishers and representatives from countries that have CIP programs, or plan to begin them, will attend the August, 1982 conference. A CLR grant supports preparation and distribution of preliminary studies, conference papers, and a final report.

International Standard Bibliographic Description (ISBD)

A five-year review of the International Standard Bibliographic Descriptions is being conducted by IFLA. The purpose is to review, rather than revise the texts. Changes will be made only to improve clarity and consistency of the texts. The CLR grant for the review also supports consultancy services by the director of the International Office for Universal

Bibliographic Control. Developing countries that are attempting to establish national bibliographic structures have requested this assistance, particularly for the purpose of advising on the preparation of new national bibliographies.

International Association of School Librarianship (IASL)

The IASL received a small grant to expand programming in international school librarianship on the occasion of its tenth anniversary. The Association plans to expand its publications program, widen participation by representatives from developing countries in its annual conferences, and implement cooperative activities with other international organizations.

Dewey Decimal Classification - Arabic Edition

Forest Press, publisher of the Dewey Classification, is preparing an Arabic edition of Abridged Edition 11 of the schedules. In cooperation with the Arab League Educational, Cultural, and Scientific Organization (ALESCO), the Press is attempting to assure effective Dewey coverage of Arab culture and to provide libraries in Arabic-speaking countries with a useful cataloging tool. The nearly complete text is currently under review.

Travel Grants

During fiscal 1982, several travel grants provided opportunities for professional activity that would otherwise be unavailable. IFLA received one such grant, to send an Executive Board member to the UNESCO-IFLA Congress on the Universal Availability of Publications in Paris, in May, 1982. Two senior staff members of the National Library of China (Beijing), Ms. Liu Guangwei, and Ms. Sun Peixun, received travel and support assistance for an intensive six-months' study and training period at the Library of Congress in 1982.

Rutherford D. Rogers, chair of the Programme Management Committee of IFLA, received funding to attend meetings of the Committee.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY RESOURCES
PROGRAM COMMITTEES, TASK FORCES,
AND PROJECT PARTICIPANTS

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